

Amplifying Children's Voices

Communications channels, content and processes that will support and facilitate the Children in Care Complaints process
– Phase Two Consultation

March 2021

Amplifying Children’s Voices Communications channels, content and processes that will support and facilitate the Children in Care Complaints process – Phase Two Consultation

Nadine Metzger
Annalise Myers
Point and Associates (Aotearoa) Limited

Lyn Doherty
Ohomairangi Trust

This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International.

This license requires that reusers give credit to the creator. You are free to distribute, remix, adapt, and build upon the material in any medium or format, even for commercial purposes. If you remix, adapt, or build upon the material, you must license the modified material under identical terms.

To view a copy of this license, visit <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/>

10.5281/zenodo.17744744

Contents

Executive summary	4
Introduction	7
The Survey: Who did we hear from?	8
Overarching themes.....	9
The Complaints Journey.....	11
Situation Awareness	12
Recognising the problem	12
The Need for Help.....	15
Evaluating the source of help	17
Evaluating help.....	18
Look and feel.....	19
Making a complaint	23
Getting in touch	23
The Complaints process.....	25
What matters to children and young people.....	25
During the complaints process	28
Conclusion.....	32
Appendix One: Design Checklist	33
Complaints framework	33
Guiding Principles	33
Accessibility.....	33
Responsive, relational practice.....	34
Restoration and problem solving.....	35
Communication channels	36
Website	36
Videos.....	38
Booklet	39
Poster	39
In person	40
The Complaints Process.....	40
Operational requirements	40
Engaging with children and young people.....	41
Appendix Two: Deep Dives	44

Executive summary

This report covers Phase Two of the Children's Voices research project which will support the Ombudsman to design new communications channels, content and processes that will support and facilitate the Children in Care Complaints process.

Phase two of the research involved an interactive survey with 58 care experienced children and young people, interviews with 29 care experienced young people, as well as whānau, foster carers, social workers, teachers, and youth workers, and three 'deep dives' with 17 children and young people aged between 4 and 21 years.

The research identified three overarching themes about the tools and communication channels:

- **Te ao Māori:** Tools and communication channels need to recognise, reference and pay special attention to te ao Māori.
- **Accessibility:** Tools and communication channels need to allow for varying levels of literacy (reading and writing), should be suitable for those with low levels of concentration and allow people with seeing and/or hearing difficulties to participate.
- **"Complaints:"** The term 'complaint' is culturally loaded and is likely to be a barrier to engagement with the Ombudsman.

The complaints journey

Engagement and communication tools are considered within a complaints journey framework. The research found that:

Situation awareness and recognising there is a problem:

Raising awareness of the rights of children and young people in care will help them recognise when there is a problem and when they need help to deal with it. More than one quarter of children and young people surveyed are not aware of their rights in care. In addition, very few adults (approximately one in 10) were aware of the rights of children in care.

Most care experienced children and young people indicated that they wanted to learn about their rights through several different methods, including film, in person, from a website or in a printed format.

Seeking help

Actively seeking help is a necessary precursor to making a complaint. Not all children and young people would seek help if they were sad, angry, or worried about something that happened in care, with two in five (43%) saying they would *not* seek help. Reasons they gave

Children's voices and the Children in Care Complaints process

for this included not wanting to be a bother, or thinking they could solve the problem themselves. Our interviews with trusted adults suggest non-help seeking behaviour may also be driven by a desire to preserve relationships and not stir up an already unstable situation.

One of the enablers of help seeking is having the support of trusted people; young people told us they are most likely to first talk to a member of their whānau or family (71%) or a friend (53%) if they were worried about something that happened in care.

Once they have determined that help is needed, children and young people told us they would likely start searching for information and sources of help on the internet or asking a friend. Trusted adults would also likely begin using an internet search.

Evaluating the source of help

Before deciding whether to proceed with contact with the Ombudsman, care experienced children and young people (and/or their trusted adult or support person) need reassurance that it's OK to get in touch, clear information about confidentiality and privacy, clear information about the source of help (who the Ombudsman is, what the powers of the Ombudsman are, that they are independent of Oranga Tamariki), an understanding of the process, a description of who they might be getting in contact with, and reassurance that they will be listened to and taken seriously.

This information could be conveyed in written form (i.e., via a website) and through storytelling using film and other visual tools.

Making a complaint

Once they have found the information they need and made the decision to get in touch, most young people would like to contact the Ombudsman by text message or a phone call. Not everyone wants to speak to someone when they call – one-third would like to leave a name and have someone contact them. Other forms of contact, such as a chat screen or web form should also be available. Any form of contact needs to be free, and available 24/7.

The complaints process

Children and young people see themselves as integral to sorting out the issue. They want the person helping them to listen carefully and check for understanding and then they want to resolve problems or address issues together to reduce the sense of losing control of the complaints process.

For children and young people, making a complaint is fraught with concerns of being at increased risk of negative consequences for themselves and their loved ones including younger siblings in care. For just under half, being kept safe whilst it is being sorted out is important.

Child-centred, trauma-informed communication is an essential skill for those assisting with the

Children's voices and the Children in Care Complaints process

complaints process.

Children and young people want to be updated by text, email, or phone throughout the complaints process. They do not want any decisions to be made without their input.

Other considerations

- Any child or young person who is making a complaint on their own behalf should be encouraged to get support from an advocate or other trusted adult/s.
- Counselling may be required if children and young people disclose trauma, or if past trauma arises during the complaints process.
- Communication should be available in te reo Maori and English.
- Access to translation support is important for those with English as a second language.
- Where possible, the same person should deal with the child or young person (and/or their trusted adult/support person) throughout the complaints process.

Introduction

This report covers Phase Two of the Children's Voices research project which will support the Ombudsman to design new communications channels, content and processes that will support and facilitate the Children in Care Complaints process.

This report is focussed on these four questions:

- How children in care and their whānau and caregivers want to engage with the Ombudsman to make complaints about Oranga Tamariki;
- The preferred communication channels of children in care and their whānau and caregivers and the content they need to help them understand complaints processes;
- The help-seeking journey of children in care, and their whānau and caregivers to enable the Ombudsman to ensure content is relevant and helpful to each part of the journey.
- Help-seeking behaviours of children in care, and their whānau and caregivers, to help the Ombudsman target relevant and helpful content towards their helpers and supporters.

This report is offered in two parts. The body of the report comprises the results from the quantitative and qualitative data from Phase Two of this research (survey, interview, deep dives). Appendix One, the 'design brief', is a series of bullet points which summaries information from Phases One and Two around the complaints framework, communication channels and the complaints process. An insights document which details several complaints journeys is intended to be read alongside this document.

Method

Phase Two of this research process involved:

- An interactive survey of 58 children and young people. Children and young people could complete the survey in both English and te reo Māori and had the option to read or listen to the survey questions.
- 29 interviews with care-experienced young people, whānau, foster carers, social workers, teachers, and youth workers (whānau, foster carers, social workers, teachers, and youth workers are referred to throughout this report as 'trusted adults'.)
- A deep dive with 17 care-experienced young people aged between 4 and 21 in South and West Auckland.

Figure 1: Interactive survey (English Version)

The Survey: Who did we hear from?

Ethnicity and gender

Most participants identified as either Māori (43%) or Pakeha (45%). 18% identified as Pasifika and 14% as 'other'.

Compared with current care statistics, Pakeha and Pasifika survey participants are over-represented, and Māori are under-represented (Māori comprise 60% of children in care). Note that participants could choose more than one ethnicity, which is why totals add up to more than 100%.

Female respondents to the survey are over-represented, comprising 60% of survey respondents.

Difficulties

Half (52%) of respondents indicated they had some form of physical or cognitive difficulty. Of these, nearly half had difficulties remembering or concentrating. Other difficulties indicated were:

- Reading or writing (33%)
- Hearing (33%)
- Speaking or communicating (29%)
- Seeing (23%)
- Moving or walking (5%)

One-third experienced more than one difficulty.

Overarching themes

There are three themes that ran through the help seeking model from start to finish.

Te ao Māori

Firstly, many interviewees felt that the over-representation of tamariki and rangatahi Māori meant that any tools or communication channels needed to recognise, reference and pay special attention to te ao Māori, in particular:

- Any tools to have a look and feel (i.e., visuals, language, karakia and waiata) that felt familiar and welcoming to tamariki, rangatahi and whānau.
- Visuals and language to prioritise the collective over the individual.
- Option to participate in the process using te reo Māori.
- Option to read and receive information in te reo Māori.
- Helpers with a good understanding of tikanga Māori and children's rights within whānau, hapu and iwi.

Accessibility

Accessibility was vitally important for any tools used either to communicate with or engage young people. Half of all children and young people we surveyed indicated they had difficulties which would make reading or communicating difficult. This research used an ACASI (audio-computer-assisted self-interviewing) tool developed by Viewpoint to make the survey more accessible for children and young people with communication difficulties. ACASI tools:

- are useful for aiding literacy difficulties,
- improve quality of information by increasing response to sensitive questions,
- decrease socially desirable responses (e.g., children and young people telling adults what they think they want to hear),
- are a suitable method for data collection where formal education is low.

The researchers were able to observe young people using this tool. Their overall impression was the sense of accomplishment that the young people displayed after they had engaged with and completed the survey. The researchers noted that the introduction to the survey – which can only be read on screen and not read out loud (the consent statement), was a barrier to engagement and the young people required help with this part. A couple of the young people also had to be shown how to use the tool. It only needed to be demonstrated once, however, and after that they confidently completed it on their own.

"Complaints"

Lastly, the word 'complaint' was problematic for many of the people we heard from. Young

Children's voices and the Children in Care Complaints process

people likened making a complaint to 'snitching' or 'moaning' and felt that after making a complaint people would regard them as troublemakers.

Our interviewees from various Pacific and Asian cultures also told us that cultural frameworks around 'respect' and/or deference to elders mean Pacific and Asian peoples unlikely to complain.

"Having children vocally voicing their concerns, and questioning authority, is so against Asian cultural norms." Trusted adult.

Children and young people want to problem solve, resolve, preserve and protect relationships, and protect the mana of everyone involved. The kinds of outcomes that young people want from a complaints process is reflected in the language that could be used to describe a process. Words like "reconnecting", "resolving", "reaching solutions" "problem solving" may be more effective in getting children and young people to come forward. One young person suggested that it could simply be called "help."

The Complaints Journey

Figure 2: Model of help-seeking towards a complaint resolution

Situation Awareness

Awareness that something is not right is the first step on the complaints journey. Children, young people, and adults we spoke to all asked for clarity around what makes a fair complaint. Young people did not want to be perceived as "moaners" or "snitches".

Although it is out of scope of this project, some trusted adults felt that children in care needed better access to therapeutic support and counselling to raise their knowledge or emotional awareness of their needs, or a more proactive system where children in care were reached out to or followed up monthly to check for issues.

Recognising the problem

Getting information on their rights is vital for all children and young people in care to help them recognise when there is a problem and when they need help to deal with it.

Most trusted adults were concerned that children and young people in care were at increased risk when they were unaware of their rights. They felt that raising the awareness of children's rights among all children and adults would go some way towards helping children in care better identify situations where they might need help. A raised awareness of the rights of children in care needed to occur among both children in care and people who care-experienced children and young people might turn to for support, such as friends, cousins, siblings, or trusted adults.

Some of the trusted adults we spoke to felt there was a need for adults to bring complaints on behalf of children and young people about professional misconduct from individuals or groups of professionals within the care system. They wanted a complaints process which could respond to adults laying complaints on behalf of children and young people who are at increased risk because they:

- are separated from their whanau networks,
- are babies and young children,
- live in residential care,
- experience mental illness and/or have disabilities,
- are in crisis due to traumatic event,
- have a relationship with person involved in the complaint which the child or young person may not want to risk by laying a complaint themselves.

Their biggest question was whether the complaints system would respond to complaints made on behalf of children without their involvement or consent.

National Care Standards

The National Care Standards, which came into effect in 2019, include a child-friendly Statement of Rights to ensure every child and young person in care understands what they are entitled to.

Children and young people in care have the right to:

- know why they are in care.
- live somewhere safe.
- get to know their caregivers.
- have a say in everything that is about them.
- have contact with whānau, hapu, iwi, family, friends.
- know who they are and where they come from.
- have visits from their social worker.
- have a plan for now and the future.
- privacy and confidentiality.
- make a complaint, share a worry or give feedback.
- have an advocate.
- get help after leaving care.

Tamariki Maori have additional rights. Oranga Tamariki must:

- Involve whānau, hapu and iwi in decisions
- First try and find a placement with whānau, hapu or iwi
- Connect tamariki to their cultural identity and keep them connected with whānau, hapu, iwi.

Awareness of rights

Awareness of rights is relatively low.

Just under one-quarter of care experienced children and young people who completed our survey are not aware of their rights in care, with 16% of these telling us they do not know their rights, and 12% do not know what 'rights' are. Half (50%) know some of their rights, and the remainder (22%) know all their rights.

Only around one in every 10 trusted adults we interviewed were aware of the rights of children in care.

Figure 3: Children and young people's awareness of rights in care (%) (n=58)

Currently, information about the rights of New Zealand children in care can be found on the Oranga Tamariki website (as an online or printed book or poster, with both pictures and words), or on the VOYCE Whakarongo Mai website (which is words only).¹

Learning about their rights

Children and young people we surveyed wanted to learn about their rights through a video (50%) or to have someone go over them in person. Most children and young people chose multiple options for learning about their rights, suggesting that a printed format backed up with information on a website, along with a video, could be useful.

Figure 4: How children and young people would like to learn about their rights (%)

¹ We are unclear as to the reach of any posters, books or pamphlets, however, only one young person interviewed had seen the "My Rights My Voice" book.

Children's voices and the Children in Care Complaints process

Reaching children and young people through social media such as tik tok, or advertising on YouTube would be the most effective way to let them know they had rights, and what those rights are. Trusted adults also wanted to see physical information such as posters/pamphlets in places where children in care might be e.g., schools, OT offices, places where Family Group Conferences take place, and youth courts. One felt that integrating a rights-based focus into the school curriculum (including information on the role of the Ombudsman) would help to normalise the concept of rights among all children. Another thought that the Ombudsman could visit all residential homes and justice centres and be introduced directly to children and young people in care.

Make a rights discussion a thing with children and caregivers so that everyone is on same page.

Ideally, any rights information given to care experienced children and young people will be documented (not just communicated verbally) so that children and young people can refer to it as often as they need. A collective understanding and acknowledgement of rights, between the child/young person, their lawyer, social worker, and carer is also important.

The Need for Help

Seeking help

Actively seeking help is a necessary precursor to making a complaint. Only six out of 10 children and young people surveyed (57%) said they would seek help if they were worried.

Figure 5: Percentage of children and young people who would seek help if they were sad, angry or worried about something that happened in care.

Those who would not want to do anything about it said they would want to be a bother, or they could solve the problem themselves.

Both trusted adults we spoke to and the evidence suggests children demonstrate they are unhappy in different ways depending on their developmental and chronological age and experiences of trauma. They may react to a situation by internalising the situation, blaming themselves or displaying behaviours such as outbursts of violence and antisocial behaviour. This behaviour may be considered a type of help seeking. Some thought may need to be given to identifying these behaviours and letting care experienced children and

I felt that by complaining I was being a nuisance in a way, like a burden and people would think that I was moaning about something. Young person

young people know that it is OK to let others know they are unhappy and need help to resolve issues, and that they will be kept safe whilst doing so.

Who they would seek help from

Young people interviewed told us that to reach out for help they need the support of others they trust, especially trusts peers, friends and whānau. They are most likely to talk to a member of their whānau or family (71%) or a friend (53%) if they were worried about something that happened in care. They are significantly more likely to talk to these people than they are to a counsellor or therapist, their social worker, caregiver or foster parent, or their teacher.

Figure 6: Who young people would talk to if they were worried about something that happened in care (%)

Finding information

If they thought their rights were not being respected, children and young people in care would prefer to find out more information (e.g., what rights are being breached, where they might get help to deal with the problem) by talking to someone in person (83%). Given other survey answers, it is likely this person is a whānau or family member, or a friend.

Figure 7: Where young people would go to seek information about rights breaches.

Evaluating the source of help

Finding help

Most people would start looking online to find out what or who might be able to help.

Children and young people are most likely to search the internet (62%) or ask a friend (50%) when searching for a person or place who could help them (Figure 8).

Figure 8: Finding someone who could help once it is determined help is needed.

When approached for help, trusted adults are most likely to search online, with most telling us they would use Google as a first step. They also want to be able to access help through the Oranga Tamariki, Ministry of Social Development, Office of the Children's Commissioner,

Ministry of Justice, Citizens Advice, Community Law and Ombudsman websites.²

Evaluating help

Evaluating the source of help

Both children and trusted adults want to evaluate the source of help before proceeding. The priority information they require before deciding to proceed with contact is:

- Reassurance that it's OK to get in contact.
- Clear information and reassurance around confidentiality, privacy and anonymity.
- The availability of advocates.
- Information about the Ombudsman:
 - Who are they?
 - What is their power to act and resolve? Are they neutral (i.e., not a part of Oranga Tamariki)?
 - What difference would their involvement make?
- A description of who they will be speaking to when they lay the complaint.
- Reassurance that children and young people will be listened to and what they say will be taken seriously. Trusted helpers would also like:

"reassurance that the child would be believed, respected, treated with kindness and empathy and compassion." (Trusted adult)

You would want them to list a description about themselves and how they have gone through something similar. Or even just how they are as a person

Young person

In addition to this, there should be a series of FAQ's, to answer questions such as:

- What the process looks like.
- Who can lay a complaint?
- How much involvement is required of a child or young person if a complaint is made on their behalf (e.g., do they need to give permission?)
- What evidence and types of evidence might be required?
- An estimate of how much time might be involved (some of the trusted adults wanted to weigh up the value of the time involved versus the likelihood of success)
- Expected timeframes.

² Most of these websites already appear at the top of google searches when the term "complaint Oranga Tamariki" is used. It may be valuable to get consistent information on each of these sites around the children and young people's complaints processes in the event a child or young person goes to one of the other websites.

Children's voices and the Children in Care Complaints process

- How and where to make a complaint
- Exactly what steps are involved in the process (with visuals)
- Is there a process to go through before going to the Ombudsman? (i.e., do we need to go to OT first?)

Storytelling is one of the primary methods that trusted adults felt information could be communicated to children and young people. Information that could be conveyed through storytelling includes:

- how the Ombudsman listens and responds
- how similar complaints have been dealt with - preferably from the experience of a complainant.
- changes that have happened as a result of other complaints.

Most trusted adults felt that the best child and young person-friendly format for this information would be videos and visual tools. The video (or videos) would:

- Feature, or be fronted by children and young people.
- Be warm and friendly.
- Feature the Ombudsman and any staff who complainants may have contact with

Some form of translated material would also be useful.

Look and feel

As already suggested, videos should be a key part of the communications tool. Most interviewees and deep dive participants were split as to whether these should be in the form of animated cartoons or real people.

Trusted adults and young people wanted the look and feel of the tools to have positive cultural references to Maori and Pacific culture e.g., visuals, language, karakia, values and waiata. They wanted the people in the tools to show the value of whānau relationships and the collective rather than the individual (i.e., young people in the deep dives were more likely to choose groups of people or animals "supporting each other", than they were individuals). They also wanted to see the diversity of Ombudsmen team members. This would help them decide to reach out for help.

Deep dives

West Auckland

Three deep dives were conducted in West Auckland and South Auckland, with a 17 males and females aged 4-21. Most (14) were Māori, with 1 Pakeha and two Pasifika participants. 13 participants had care-experience.

Children’s voices and the Children in Care Complaints process

The purpose of the deep dives was to understand the kinds of colours and characters that appealed to young people. Below is a summary of what they told us, a full list of ‘mood boards’ and why things were chosen can be found in Appendix Two.

- **Colour** – natural ‘soft’ colours dominate the colour choices. There were lots of references to nature and experiences in nature (sky, water, bush) in the children and young people’s commentary. Three older participants (14+) used colours to describe the idea of moving from dark to light, where darker hues represent a problem and lighter hues reflect that a problem has been shared and therefore the load is lightened. Interestingly very few picked and stuck to ‘favourite’ colours – and those that did were typically younger participants (purple was the most frequent favourite colour chosen). When most talked about colours, they talked about how the colours made them feel. Being in nature, for example, is a good feeling (hence the dominance of blues and greens). Additionally, there was a sweeping theme of nostalgia that was referenced throughout as the young people mentioned memories of significant childhood places such as ‘the lookout’ and people in their lives that remind them of ‘happy’ colours which was usually the lighter and brighter colours (blues/greens).
- There was also one reference to the colours of the national Samoan flag (blue/red) which represented pride and significance of ethnicity.

These are the colours that appear most frequently (hex values below colour):

#468B9B	#86BBBD	#A5DAC8	#224689	#9FB85E	#EFE8C1	#A780AE	#C25450	#8B2F56

- **Characters** –The children and young people were shown 26 images and asked to choose those that appealed to them, and then tell us why. Interestingly, younger participants chose characters based on who they wanted to be with (many of the younger participants also named these characters e.g., ‘mum’ ‘aunty’ ‘best friend’). Older participants (15+) also chose images based on the people they wanted around them, but in addition to these they also chose images they felt reflected themselves or who they wanted to be. Some young people also choose images based on their existing knowledge of the film/cartoons that the characters originated from, for example: a young male talked about how the storyline of *Moana* reminded him of his own life journey. It’s noted that some older participants rejected characters if they looked too “babyish”.

'Supportive' characters

(The character in the high-vis jacket was most often referred to when this picture was chosen).

- "They've got each others back" - it was noted that the characters above appeared to have each other's back in support inside and outside of their perceived family unit.

Characters who reflect who they want to be ("proud", "strong", "fierce")

- **Culture** - In all instances, the characters had strong cultural references such as tattoos and body adornments. We were told that many of the characters were chosen because they felt familiar, they reminded them of themselves or the people around them. The young people also reflected on their own cultural identity. It is interesting to

note the references to the cultural climate of "life in New Zealand", "life in the islands" and "remembering your roots" as most young people gravitated towards images of the collective and extended family.

School leavers toolkit

Young people from two deep dives (both groups of young people aged 15+) watched three films from the Ombudsman school leavers toolkit. During discussion, they told us that they had gained an understanding not only about the Ombudsman, but they also appreciated that the information had come from other young people, who were teaching each other (and them). Not only that, they also appreciated that the young people were teaching the adults around them, too.

They told us:

- The cultural references in each of the films (Māori and Pacific actors, te reo subtitles, a tapa cloth in the background) made the setting instantly familiar.
- The use of humour made the Ombudsman appear more approachable.
- They particularly liked the reference to 'fairness for all.'
- All three films were clear and easy to understand.
- They related to the characters in the films and how they spoke to each other using slang.
- They found the films humorous and connected to the way humour was used in each scenario
- The facilitators noted that having the films presented as a 'series' or several brief stories that built over time was particularly helpful for young people with concentration or focus issues, who could 'take a break' in between each film to process the information.
- Overall, they felt all three films were "off the buzz" (translation: great).

Some suggestions:

- They were happy to watch something longer, particularly if it had examples or suggestions of other issues that might be taken to the Ombudsman.
- They would have like to have seen a story involving a 'collective' approach to the Ombudsman with the young people having support from family or friends.
- One Samoan participant would have liked some Samoan subtitles or language references. Note that this student couldn't speak Samoan – but he wanted to see his language represented in the same way te reo was represented.
- One of the groups asked for another series of films that introduced the team who might be handling the complaints. They wanted a sense of reciprocity i.e. if the investigator is getting to know them (and their support people), then they would like to know about the investigator, particularly who they are, where they come from and why

they do this work.

- There was mention that they would like to see more insight into what the working environment of the Ombudsman's office looks like
- One group needed further explanation after the film about what "local and central government" meant. Concrete examples such as schools, board of trustees, Oranga Tamariki, hospitals might make more sense to these young people.
- The facilitators also noted that music was very important to the groups. In one group in particular young people were playing music (on a piano or through their phones) and dancing to music.

Making a complaint

Most of the young people told us they needed the support of trusted adults when laying a complaint. Making a complaint was fraught with concerns of being at increased risk of negative consequences for themselves and their loved ones including younger siblings in care.

Getting in touch

Children and young people

Once they've made the decision to get in touch, most young people would like to do so by text message, or a phone call (Figure 9).

Besides text messaging, phone was one of the most preferred methods to get in touch with the Ombudsman. Not everyone wants to speak to someone when they call - 33% would like to leave a name and have someone then contact them (like scheduling a call back).

One in five (21%) would get in contact via a web form, which is the current means of giving feedback/making a complaint (besides visiting an Oranga Tamariki office in person).

They would have like "request a helper" and then you would message them then they would send back a message.

Figure 9: How young people would like to get in touch with the Ombudsman

Trusted adults

Once they have found the information they need, most trusted adults indicated they would prefer to phone or email if they were to make contact on behalf of a young person. They felt a phone call would be most useful to get immediate help on whether a complaint was warranted, the potential process, and advice on how to involve the child or young person. Email was also preferred, as it left a paper trail.

Methods

Most trusted adults felt that the information required from the initial contact with the young person should be extremely simple, i.e., name, phone number and preferred contact method. This information could be texted, left in a phone message, or submitted via a webform.

It was felt that children and young people would be more likely to want to get in contact if they could see bio’s of the people helping them or even use these to choose a person they wanted to help them.

Maybe a little form where you could tick some boxes so you don't have to write too much, but you could get it in quickly? So you don't have to write the whole scenario, it might be 'I want to make a complaint', 'I live in Auckland' etc. and then you just send it off. Trusted adult.

Some trusted adults suggested that the role of children and young people's helplines (e.g., Youthline, Kidsline, What's Up, thelowdown) should be considered. Potential uses of helplines could be:

- Refer complaints.
- 'Triage' the initial contact.
- Referral channel for any contact from a child or young person which doesn't fit the 'complaint' criteria.

The Complaints process

What matters to children and young people

Trusted adults told us the first interaction is the most important, and often determines whether the helper gains (or loses) the ongoing engagement and trust of children and young people and those that support them.

Attending to what children and young people told us they need when making a complaint may assist the process of building trust.

First and foremost, children and young people see themselves as integral to sorting out the issue. They want to resolve problems or address issues together to reduce the sense of losing control of the complaints process, and they want to know how those helping them will be accountable for creating positive outcomes through resolving the issue. This includes situations when children and young people's ideas or needs differ from those they are close to or trust. They want the person helping them to listen carefully and check for understanding. Then, they want to be part of the solution. They want someone to say 'hey, here's some things we could do. What do you think?'

Figure 10: What is important to children and young people when they tell someone about what's going on.

Listening and checking for understanding

Many young people who begin a complaints process are likely to have had previous poor experiences with communicating. This includes not feeling heard, not being believed, or taking a risk and speaking up only to have nothing happen (or to have negative consequences happen). It is understandable then, that the most important thing to the children and young people we spoke with is that the person helping them listens to them and then checks that they understand what the child or young person is telling them.

The stories these children have told about the abuse they have been through -it becomes the norm. If they actually met someone who really

A reasonable number of care-experienced tamariki and rangatahi are likely to have specific speech, language and communication needs.³ This is supported by research which identified oral communication difficulties in over 60% of young people in the criminal justice system in Australia and the UK.⁴ Recent research from NZ also established that 64% of the young people assessed in a youth justice residence context had significant language impairment compared

³ The communication needs of looked after children. (2018). *Adoption & Fostering*, 42(1), 86–90.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/0308575918760472>

⁴ Bryan, K., Freer, J. and Furlong, C. (2007) Language and Communication Difficulties in Juvenile Offenders.

International Journal of Language & Communication Disorders, 42, 505-520.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/13682820601053977>

Children's voices and the Children in Care Complaints process

with only 10% of control peers.⁵ Among the young people we surveyed, 47% indicated they had one or more difficulties with seeing (13%), hearing (16%), remembering or concentrating (24%), speaking or communicating (13%) and reading or writing (18%).

Many of the trusted adults told us that child-centred, trauma-informed communication was an essential skill for those assisting with the complaints process. In their experience, children, particularly those who have experienced trauma, don't often tell the whole story at once, and professionals need skills to help them both tell the story, and the patience to keep believing them when the story develops and changes.

There are resources and skills that can assist professionals to adapt their own communication, processes and resources to enable participation of children and young people with communication difficulties. Talking mats, for example, are a reflective listening tool that can help people of all ages and abilities have a conversation on a specific topic, and training is available through organisations such as Talking Trouble or Skylight Trust to assist professionals working with young people, particularly those who may have experienced trauma.

We heard that boys and young men have particular communication needs. "Interrogation" style interviews will not work. When meeting in person, care should be taken to:

- Reduce eye contact.
- Place your body at an angle – directly facing the young person can be threatening.
- Move. Some form of movement (shooting hoops, walking) may help relax the young person.
- Provide a secondary form of communication such as drawing or writing.

What younger children look for in a helper

Younger children aged 4-12 who participated in one of the deep dives identified the qualities they want in someone who helps them. They wanted someone who:

- listens well;
- is friendly;
- have a nice tone of voice;
- is kind,
- uses nice words,
- is helpful,
- is supportive.

They told us that if the helper has all these qualities then they could be any gender and any ethnicity.

⁵ Lount, S., Hand, L., Purdy, S.L., and France, A (2017) Tough talk: Youth offenders' perceptions of communicating in the Youth Justice system in New Zealand. Australian and New Zealand Journal of Criminology. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0004865817740404>

During the complaints process

For children and young people, what matters most to them during the complaints process is being kept updated. They don't want any decisions to be made without their input. Half would like the same person to support them the whole time.

Safety

Nearly half of all children and young people surveyed told us that it was important that they are kept safe while their problem is being sorted out (48%). Those we spoke to told us they were fearful of consequences of speaking out. They were afraid of getting in trouble, or being moved from their placement, and one said they would "keep quiet" if they felt the consequence of reaching out would be greater than the reward. They worry they will be "snubbed off", treated as a nuisance or not taken seriously.

Trusted adults are worried about the professional consequences of helping a child or young person make a complaint. They spoke about being known as a "troublemaker" or being "blacklisted" by Oranga Tamariki. Those who work in residential homes are afraid this might affect their funding. Two foster carers, who were regular carers who cared for a number of children, told us they had not had any children placed with them for three years after making a complaint. In the words of one carer: "Half of me wants to lay a complaint, and the other half is like if I do lay a complaint are they going to bite back. It's like poking a bear". Trusted adults are not only worried about consequences from Oranga Tamariki; one worker in a residential home had witnessed staff members bully others who helped children understand their rights.

Trusted adults we spoke to suggested that the helper check at every interaction that the child/young person is safe and OK to proceed. In the first interaction, they should find out if there is a trusted adult who can help and if not, help them identify one, or refer them to an advocate.

New Zealand's Vulnerable Children's Act 2014 requires organisations who work with children to have a child protection policy and to have this available on the organisation's website.

Information

At the beginning of the complaints process, one young person told us that they wanted the person helping them to:

"talk to me about what they're going to do and the days at which they would be available and then all of the ideas that they will bring, like how they're going to work with you, how they will message and talk to you, their boundaries."

Those who make a complaint – be they trusted adults on behalf of a child or young person, or a child or young person themselves, need information about their rights during the process, including:

- Their right to access the information that is gathered.
- How their information will be kept safe.
- Their right to withdraw.
- (If they wish to remain anonymous) their right to anonymity.

Other information they need:

- What other parties will be involved. Trusted helpers advised that ALL parties who are contacted or spoken to as part of the complaint be approved by the complainant first, primarily for safety.
- Time frames
- How they will be kept updated – this should be negotiated with the complainant. Young people would most prefer to be kept updated by text or email (see Figure 11)⁶
- When follow-up will occur (e.g., weekly? Fortnightly? when new information is received?)
- Boundaries of the help and the helper e.g., calling out of hours, whether meeting in person is appropriate.

Much of this information may need to be repeated more than once and should be communicated both verbally and in written form.

⁶ Whilst keeping in mind that children and young people would prefer to keep in contact via text message or email – and least preferred social media contact - trusted adults who have a lot of interaction with children in care advised that contact through social media is sometimes appropriate, particularly if the young person has a phone plan with limited text messaging capacity. Contact through social media direct messaging could be something that is negotiated with children and young people during the complaints process.

Figure 11: How children and young people would like to be kept updated during the complaints process.

Access to support

Advocates and support people

Any child or young person who is making a complaint on their own behalf should be encouraged to get support from an advocate or other trusted adult/s. Some suggestions from trusted adults included:

It could be a teacher a school counsellor, just someone that the child trusts to have their back is implemented in that whole process. It may be they suggest someone that they would like that information to be shared with.

They need a 'touch base' or 'go to' person for reassurance - could be VOYCE? Like a security blanket who could walk alongside them.

When we surveyed children and young people in care, they told us that friends are integral to their help seeking. There could be value in involving friends as support people in a complaints process (although additional support from an advocate or other trusted adult should also be encouraged).

Counselling

Counselling may be required if children and young people disclose trauma, or if past trauma arises during the complaints process. Care should be taken to ensure that young people have access to counselling support during and after the complaints process. As one trusted adult said:

After a complaint process there is the possibility of feeling quite low, some people may feel elevated or may feel in a low mood. So, make sure that you do have supportive people around them.

Translators

Both young people and trusted adults felt all communication should be available in Te Reo Maori and English and include tools for those with disabilities. Access to translation support is important for those with English as a second language. Having key documents translated into languages such as Samoan, Tongan, Mandarin, Thai could also be helpful.

Consistency

Consistency is important. Half of the children and young people surveyed (49%) said they wanted the same person to support them the whole time during the complaints process. Trusted adults advised that if the person dealing with the complaint changes, there should be a handover process involving the exiting helper, the new helper and the complainant.

Appearance

While it may seem a minor consideration, trusted adults told us that the appearance of the helper when meeting face to face can influence the engagement of children and young people and someone who dresses like "a lawyer or a professional" may be "off-putting". See also cultural considerations.

Conclusion

The participants in this research project offered very clear insights and information as to what they wanted to see represented in the communications channels, content and processes that will support and facilitate the Children in Care Complaints process.

It is clear that for children and young people to arrive at the Ombudsman, they must first have some awareness of their rights. Children, young people and their trusted adults are most likely to use the internet to search for help. When they land on the help page, they want to see something that looks like people and spaces where they feel safe. Colours are soft and natural, not bright and garish. They want a space where culture, particularly tikanga Māori, is respected and celebrated.

Before they decide to contact the Ombudsman, children, young people and their trusted adults want reassurance that they will be believed, respected and treated with kindness, empathy and compassion. They want to know that they are safe, and that their information is safe. They would like to understand who the Ombudsman is, and the likelihood of their making a difference.

For children and young people, getting in contact with the Ombudsman is a big step, fraught with concerns of being at increased risk of negative consequences. The contact process therefore needs to be very simple, such as a phone call, text message or contact form. Any contact must be acknowledged. The presence of an adult support person or advocate is important, as is acknowledging and including other supporters such as friends or siblings. For infants and young children there needs to be clear information and processes for adults bringing complaints on their behalf. There needs to be a sense of urgency to resolve complaints as quickly as possible to reduce negative impacts on the child's wellbeing.

During the complaints process, children and young people want to feel heard. They want to work together with the Ombudsman to resolve problems or address issues to reduce the sense of losing control. They ask that they are kept updated, and that any decisions made include their views. Most of all, they want things to be restored and resolved without damaging their relationships.

Appendix One: Design Checklist

This information is a series of bullet-pointed summaries which draw on evidence from Phase One (evidence review, interviews with professionals) and Phase Two (survey of children and young people, interviews with children, young people, whānau and trusted adults, and deep dive focus groups). It is best read in conjunction with these two reports to provide context.

Complaints framework

Guiding Principles

1. **Whaipainga (beneficence).** Both the research and solution should be of primary benefit to children and young people. Their use should result in positive change.
2. **Kaitiakitanga (guardianship and protection).** Harm to children and young people must not occur either through the research or use of the tools.
3. **Aro ā-tamariki (child-centred).** Development of the solution must involve children and young people and must be easy and safe for children and young people to use.
4. **Whakaoranga (restorative).** The research and the solution should recognise children and young people's experience of trauma. The solution should be focussed on restoration and healing.
5. **Tūāpāpā ā-tikanga (rights-based).** The research and the solution should recognise and promote the rights of children and young people protected in conventions such as The UN Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCROC), Article 7 of the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD) and Articles 21 and 22 of the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples (UNDRIP).
6. **Mana taurite (equity).** All children and young people should have equal access to the processes regardless of their abilities and/or means. Equity is about equity of outcome as much as access to a process and requires being free of conscious and unconscious bias.

For more information please see pages 5 – 13 of the phase one report

Accessibility

Any information needs to be provided to children in a way that can be understood by the very young and those with special needs (including physical, cognitive and behavioural challenges).

For children with language or communication difficulties, or for whom English is not their

preferred language, specialist help is likely to be required to ensure that they have equal access to the complaints system. An ACASI (audio-computer-assisted self-interviewing) tool may be one way of increasing accessibility to the complaints system.

Any online information should meet minimum [web accessibility requirements](#), particularly read out loud functions.

Responsive, relational practice

It is recommended that implementing a practice framework such as āta⁷ is considered for the children in care complaints process.

"Āta" is a cultural tool to inform and guide understandings of respectfulness in relationships. It's focus is on relationships, working together, negotiating boundaries, and working to create and hold safe spaces. Children and young people indicated these mattered to them during the complaints process.

Takepū Principles	He Whakamāramatanga Definitions
Āta-haere	To be intentional and deliberate and to approach reflectively, moving with respect and integrity. It signals the act of moving with an awareness of relationships,
Āta-whakarongo	To listen with reflective deliberation. This requires patience and tolerance, giving space to listen and communicate to the heart, mind and soul of the speaker, context and environment. It requires the conscious participation of all senses, the natural inclusion of the values of trust, integrity, and respectfulness.
Āta-kōrero	To communicate and speak with clarity, requiring quality preparation and a deliberate gathering of what is to be communicated. This is to ensure a quality of presentation (kia mārama ki te kaupapa), to speak with conviction (kia pūmau ki te kaupapa), and to be focused (kia hāngai ki te kaupapa).
Āta-tuhi	To communicate and write with deliberation, needing to be constantly reflective, and knowing the purpose for writing; in this, consistently monitoring and measuring quality is implicit.

⁷ Pohatu, T. W. (2013). Āta: Growing respectful relationships. *Āta: Journal of Psychotherapy Aotearoa New Zealand*, 17(1), 13-26. DOI: 10.9791/ajpanz.2013.02 © New Zealand Association of Psychotherapists Inc.

Āta-mahi	To work diligently, with the conviction that what is being done is correct and appropriate to the tasks undertaken.
Āta-noho	To give quality time to be with people and their issues, with an open and respectful mind, heart and soul. This signals the level of integrity required in relationships.
Āta-whakaaro	To think with deliberation, allowing space for creativity, openness and reflection, the consequence of which is that action is undertaken to the best of one's ability.
Āta-whakaako	To instil knowledge and understanding deliberately. There are clear reasons why knowledge is shared – to the appropriate participants, in the required manner, time and place.
Āta-tohutohu	To instruct, monitor and correct deliberately, in which grounded knowledge is a constant and valued companion. Cultural markers such as kaitiakitanga (responsible trusteeship) are then accorded safe space to enlighten how and why relationships should be maintained.
Āta-kīnaki	To be deliberate and clear in the choice of appropriate supports to enhance positions taken.
Āta-hoki mārire	To return with respectful acknowledgement of possible consequences.
Āta-whakamārama	To inform with reflective deliberation, ensuring that the channels of communication at the spiritual, emotional and intellectual levels of the receiver are respected, understood, and valued.

Restoration and problem solving

- The word 'complaint' is problematic for children and young people, likened to 'snitching' or 'moaning.'
- Cultural frameworks around 'respect' and/or deference to elders mean Pacific and Asian peoples unlikely to complain.
- Suggested words or phrases which may be used instead:
 - Help
 - Request a helper.
 - Dealing with worries

Children's voices and the Children in Care Complaints process

- Got a problem? Let us help you solve it.
- Reaching solutions, together
- Helping to make a hard situation better.
- Reconnecting
- Problem solving,
- Resolving,
- Restoring.

Communication channels

Website

Content

- Rights in care.
- Types of complaints that can be dealt with.
- Availability of advocates (link to VOYCE website or other advocacy services if appropriate)
- Privacy, confidentiality.
- Safety.
- Reassurance that children and young people will be listened to and what they say will be taken seriously.
- Illustration of process, including timeframes (graphic journey map).
- List of possible outcomes.
- Introduce Ombudsman (the person and the role).
- Who are they?
- What is their power to act and resolve?
- Are they neutral (i.e., not a part of Oranga Tamariki)?
- What difference would their involvement make?
- Introduce investigators.

Accessibility

- Website should meet minimum [web accessibility requirements](#), particularly read out loud functions.

Help seeking / contact options:

- Toll free number.
- Text.
- Email address (more likely to be used by adults).

Children's voices and the Children in Care Complaints process

- Contact for advocacy service (who can lay a complaint on their behalf if they wish to remain anonymous)
- Simple webform
 - Name
 - Two types of contact (phone, email)
 - Best times for contact
 - Whether the person contacting is a child or young person, or adult.
 - Note 1: Webform should be maximum of one click through from the main Ombudsman site.
 - Note 2: Contact form could be preceded by: "If you wish to contact us on behalf of yourself or someone else, please leave contact details here".

Look and feel:

- Information to be brief and clear (use videos to communicate more information)
- Where possible, show groups of children and young people with friends and whānau (i.e., not children and young people on their own)
- Use (primarily) Māori and Pasifika cultural references.
- Colours (TBA after deep dives completed)

Additional content for trusted adults/helpers

- Website should be directed at children and young people in care, with separate tab for helpers.
- Helper FAQ's which cover:
 - What the process looks like.
 - Who can lay a complaint?
 - How much involvement is required of a child or young person if a complaint is made on their behalf (e.g., do they need to give permission?)
 - What evidence and types of evidence might be required?
 - An estimate of how much time might be involved (some of the trusted adults wanted to weigh up the value of the time involved versus the likelihood of success)
 - Expected timeframes.
 - How and where to make a complaint
 - Exactly what steps are involved in the process (with visuals)
 - Is there a process to go through before going to the Ombudsman? (Do they need to go to OT first?)
- Information for helpers should include clear, brief information about what to do if they are approached by a child or young person in care for help e.g.
 - Listen carefully.
 - Check for understanding.

Children's voices and the Children in Care Complaints process

- Maintain confidentiality until you have the permission of the young person to seek help from others.
- Encourage the child or young person to contact an advocate (e.g., VOYCE), and support them to do so.

Other considerations

- SEO: Ombudsman site should come top of search results (currently Citizens Advice Bureau is top result for "making a complaint about Oranga Tamariki" search).
- Remember that helpers who access the website may be peers/friends of children in care, not just adults.
- No more than three click-throughs for any information
- All other websites that contain information about Oranga Tamariki complaints process should have consistent information.

Videos

Content

- Reassurance it's OK to get in touch.
- Introduce Ombudsman.
- Introduce investigators.
- Outline process.
- Demonstrate how the Ombudsman listens and responds, how similar complaints have been dealt with (preferably from the experience of a complainant) and changes that have happened because of other complaints.
- Show possible outcomes.
- Include contact information for help (phone, text, url)

Look and feel:

- Where possible, show groups of children and young people with friends and whānau (i.e., not children and young people on their own)
- Use (primarily) Māori and Pasifika cultural references.
- Consider using both animation and real people.
- Video should feature or be fronted by children and young people.
- Be warm and friendly.
- Feature the Ombudsman and any staff who complainants may have contact with

Principles for communicating with different age groups

- Early years (birth – 6 years) children would respond to a book being read out loud, or a

Children's voices and the Children in Care Complaints process

song.

- 7–10-year-olds should respond well to positive child role models which show children making a difference to themselves and others
- Both younger and older teens should respond to communication that is high interest, low literacy (e.g., graphics, sound) providing it is not patronising or does not appear to be 'dumbed down.'

Other

- Consider brief Tik Tok clips as well as longer YouTube videos.

Booklet

Content

- Rights in care
- Introduce Ombudsman (the role).
- Reassurance it's OK to get in touch.
- Contact information for help (phone, text, url)

Look and feel:

- Where possible, show groups of children and young people with friends and whānau (i.e., not children and young people on their own).
- Use (primarily) Māori and Pasifika cultural references.

Other

- Booklet should be given to young people by social worker, carers, trusted adults.
- Could amend "My Rights My Voice booklet" to include Ombudsman contact details or produce new booklet to match look and feel of website.
- Booklet should be available in hard copy and downloaded from website.

Poster

Content

- Rights in care
- Reassurance it's OK to get in touch.

Look and feel

- Similar look and feel to booklet.

Children's voices and the Children in Care Complaints process

- For display in residential homes, youth justice centres, schools, OT offices, anywhere FCGs are held.

In person

- Workshops/meet and greets with residential homes, youth justice centres, Child and Youth help lines (Youthline, 0800 Whats Up or Kidsline).
- Presentations or webinars targeting trusted adults and professionals e.g. INVOLVE Youth Worker conference, PPTA conference, Aotearoa New Zealand Association of Social Workers, Caring Families Aotearoa conferences.

The Complaints Process

Operational requirements

Clear and reasonable time limits

- Communicated to complainants.
- Visually presented.
- Clarity on what happens next (and when).

Transparency and clarity

- Simple and straightforward.
- Speedy, constructive, agreeable solutions
- Complainants kept updated throughout the process.
- Little, if any, handoff between agencies.
- Decisions and actions clearly documented and communicated.

Strict confidentiality policies and practices

Staff training

- Child-centred, trauma-informed communication
- Handling complaints with sensitivity, respect, empathy and courtesy.
- Cultural safety, and how to make a complaints process accessible and welcoming to children and young people from all cultural backgrounds.
- Confidentiality principles.
- Interviewing or communicating with children and young people who have experienced harm or trauma.
- Interviewing or communicating with young people who have communication

Children's voices and the Children in Care Complaints process

difficulties (e.g., talking mats).

- Interviewing or communicating with vulnerable children and young people, such as those who are living with disabilities, homeless, members of minority groups, refugees or new migrants.
- How to maintain transparency with the young person and manage their expectations in terms of what is and isn't possible.
- How, when and in what ways to involve whānau when appropriate.

Cultural safety.

- An ecological and holistic approach using and incorporating whakawhānaungatanga (nurturing relationships), manaakitanga (care) and kaitiakitanga (guardianship, trust).
- Refer to āta framework on page 26

Other

- Clarity around whether trusted adults can bring complaints on the behalf of children and young people in care about professional misconduct from individuals or groups of professionals within the care system, without the involvement or consent of the child or young person in special circumstances (e.g., babies, young children, disabilities, children and young people in residential care or are in crisis, or where there is a relationship that needs to be protected).

Engaging with children and young people

Principles of engagement

- Where possible, use a collective rather than individual approach, ensuring child or young person has additional support from trusted adult or advocate.
- Listen actively and check for understanding.
- If a trusted adult or advocate is involved, check any previous trauma with them (prior to interacting with child or young person) to avoid triggers.
- Work out solutions with the child or young person.
- Keep them safe while it is being sorted out.
- Keep them updated.
- Ensure any decisions include their views.

General

- Where possible, keep members of team consistent.
- Use communication assistance where required.
- For Māori and Pacific children beginning with a prayer or karakia may be appropriate

Children's voices and the Children in Care Complaints process

- Do not expect immediate, full disclosure of sensitive issues.

In person engagement

- Do not face the child or young person directly.
- Do not expect eye contact.
- Use props to help tell the story (e.g., post-it notes, talking mats).

Information required by children and young people during process

- Their right to access the information that is gathered.
- How their information will be kept safe.
- Their right to withdraw.
- (If they wish to remain anonymous) their right to anonymity.
- What other parties will be involved (Any party contacted or spoken to as part of the investigation should be approved by the complainant first, primarily for safety).
- Time frames.
- How they will be kept updated.

Other support that may be required

- Counselling – both during and after the complaints process
- Translators

Engaging with babies, young children and minors who cannot speak for themselves.

It is essential that any complaints process uphold the human rights of those who cannot speak for themselves.⁸ Babies and young children, by reason of their physical and mental immaturity and absolute dependence need special safeguards and care.

- There needs to be clear information and processes for receiving complaints from adults on behalf of babies, young children and minors who cannot speak for themselves.
- Part of the process should be understanding the motivations of the adult making the complaint and what they or the child stand to benefit. Is it in the best interests of the child?
- The process should collect the voices of others around the child (biological parents, whānau, caregivers).

⁸ The United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child, with reference to the World Association for Infant Mental Health (WAIMH) Position Paper on the Rights of Infants - (Perspectives IMH 13 May 2016.)

Children's voices and the Children in Care Complaints process

- Process and resolution must be fast.

Appendix Two: Deep Dives

Note, CE denotes care experience.

Male - aged 14 (CE)

- These colours are 'happy'. Reminds me of family.
- Panda cartoon - like the group, they've 'got each other's back'. Supportive
- Likes the background of the other picture - reminds of roots and belonging.

Pasifika Male, aged 12 (CE)

- Colours - like the colours of the Samoan Flag
- People - tattoo on arm, the idea of family.
- Other picture looks like students my age.

Male (CE)

- "Just chose" the colours
- Likes cartoons, anime
- Likes cultural references (background, tattoos on other pictures)

Māori Male, aged 20yrs (CE)

- Dark to light colours represent where you are coming from (the dark), and where you aspire to be (the light).
- The character (Maui from the Moana movie) "never gives up".
- Comments "Only time you should look back is to see how far you've come". "One bad chapter doesn't mean your story's over."

Children’s voices and the Children in Care Complaints process

Māori Male, aged 20yrs (CE)

- The male character “reminds me of myself”
- The colours are ‘natural’ and a reminder of fun times spent outside

Pakeha Male aged 20yrs (CE)

- [This young man needed to step out during the process and didn’t talk about his choices].

Maori Female, aged 17 (CE)

- Colours are simple. Purple is a ‘favourite’ colour.
- Likes the young and fun characters

Maori Female, aged 21 (CE)

- These are favourite colours
- Image reminds her of herself and her culture
- Other images being with people who care about you is important

8 years old

- Wants support from mum and dad
- Person helping needs to be kind and use nice words.

Female, aged 12

- Whānau should support through process.
- Ombudsman helper should listen well and be friendly.

Female, 14 years old (CE)

- Wants support from mum, sister and friend
- Wants to phone Ombudsman and talk to a young person/peer to be on the end of the phone.

Male, aged 9 (CE)

- Would like support from Uncle.
- Ombudsman helper should listen well and be friendly.

Children's voices and the Children in Care Complaints process

10 year old (CE)

- Wants support from best friend, uncle and siblings
- Helper should listen and be friendly.

4 year old

- Wants mum there
- These are favourite colours.

14 year old

- Needs mum and best friend to be there through the process
- Wants to talk to someone on the phone.

12 year old

- Wants support from mum, auntie, nanny and uncle.
- Needs helper to be supportive

